

Complementary Feeding Practices and Nutritional Status of Children Aged 6-23 Months in a Tertiary Care Hospital of Kolhan Region of Jharkhand.Ruchi Jha¹, Ajay Raj²¹Assistant Professor, Dept. of Paediatrics, M.G.M. Medical College, Jamshedpur, Jharkhand²Professor, Dept. of Paediatrics, M.G.M. Medical College, Jamshedpur, Jharkhand

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Abstract:

The age of 6-23 months period is called the window of opportunity and is the important stage to optimize child growth and development in order to prevent malnutrition, including wasting, underweight and stunting, as well as the negative consequences in adulthood. Adequate breastfeeding and complementary feeding practices can prevent under-five mortality by 19%. Studies have shown that growth faltering starts as early as 3 months up to 2 years of age. Even with optimum breastfeeding, children are at risk of being stunted if they do not receive adequate dietary amount, diversity, and meal frequency after 6 months of age. During infancy and early childhood (birth to 2 years), adequate amount of appropriate nutrition has paramount importance for full development of children's human potential.

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Introduction

The age of 6-23 months period is called the window of opportunity and is the important stage to optimize child growth and development in order to prevent malnutrition, including wasting, underweight and stunting, as well as the negative consequences in adulthood [1]. Adequate breastfeeding and complementary feeding practices can prevent under-five mortality by 19%. [2] Studies have shown that growth faltering starts as early as 3 months up to 2 years of age. Even with optimum breastfeeding, children are at risk of being stunted if they do not receive adequate dietary amount, diversity, and meal frequency after 6 months of age. [3]. NHFS -5 suggest that percentage of children under 5 who are stunted and wasted are as high as 39.6% and 22.4% respectively. [4]. Percentage of children receiving adequate diet according to NHFS 5 is only 10%. Complementary feeding practices vary widely among the regions and are guided by the maternal beliefs and regional practices. The present communication examines the practices of mothers regarding complementary feeding including dietary diversity, frequency, and acceptable diet. [5]

Objectives:

- To determine the complementary feeding practices, and nutritional status of children aged 6–23 months.
- To study the association between adequate complementary feeding practices and nutritional status of children aged 6 months -24

months attending MGM Medical College and Hospital. [6,7]

- To study the percentage prevalence of minimum acceptable diet (composite indicator of minimum dietary diversity and minimum meal frequency) in study population.

Plan of Work and Techniques to be Used:**Study Design:** Hospital cross sectional study.**Study Population:** children from 6 months -23 months attending Paediatrics OPD and Immunization Centre from July, 2022 to June 2023.**Settings and Places:** All children from 6 months – 23 months attending Paediatrics OPD and Immunization Centre in MGM Medical College Hospital Jamshedpur.**Inclusion Criteria:**

- Children from 6-23 months attending Paediatrics OPD, IPD and Immunization Clinics.
- Mothers who are willing to participate in the study.

Exclusion Criteria

- Children born prematurely. (<37 weeks of gestation).
- Children with chronic illnesses.
- Children accompanied by attendants who are not aware of the child's feeding.
- Attendants not willing to participate.

Sample Size: Sample size was calculated using formula $N = P(1-p) Z^2/E^2$. Taking relative precision of 5% at 95% confidence interval, the sample is calculated to be 366. So 370 children were enrolled.

Sampling Method: Convenient Sampling.

Data Collection: After taking a written consent, using a Semi structured questionnaire, information about Personal details and Socio Demographic and Economic details were recorded. Complementary Feeding practice details were obtained from the mother and will be recorded. Nutritional status of the child were assessed by measuring weight (precision of 0.1 cm) and recumbent length using Infantometer (precision of 0.1 kg).

Training of the Interviewer: Interviewers were given adequate training about the questions of the questionnaire to maintain uniformity in data collection.

Ethical Consideration

Ethical consideration: Necessary approval was taken from the ethical committee before starting the study.

Informed Consent Statement: Informed consent was taken from the attendants of the children included in the study after explaining the purpose of the study.

Operational Definitions

- 1. Early Initiation of Breastfeeding:** infants who are put to the breast within 1 hour of birth
- 2. Exclusive Breastfeeding:** infants aged 0-5 months who are fed exclusively on breast milk, with no other food or drink, including water. The infant is, however, allowed to receive oral rehydration solution (ORS) and drops or syrups containing vitamins, minerals and medicine.
- 3. Continued Breast Feeding At 2 Years :** Children who received breastfeeding in last 24 hrs

4. Minimum Dietary Diversity: Minimum dietary diversity is present when the diet contains five or more of the following food groups:

- breast milk;
- grains, roots and tubers;
- legumes and nuts;
- dairy products (milk, yogurt, cheese);
- flesh foods (meat, fish, poultry, liver or other organs);
- eggs;
- vitamin A-rich fruits and vegetables; and
- other fruits and vegetables

5. Minimum Daily Meal Frequency: The minimum daily meal frequency is defined as:

- Twice for breastfed infants aged 6-8 months,
- Three times for breastfed children aged 9-23 months
- Four times for non-breastfed children aged 6-23 months

6. Minimum Acceptable Diet:

The composite indicator of a minimum acceptable diet is calculated from:

- The proportion of breastfed children aged 6-23 months who had at least the MDD and minimum meal frequency during the previous day; and
 - The proportion of non-breastfed children aged 6-23 months who received at least two milk feedings and had at least the MDD, not including milk feeds, and minimum meal frequency during the previous day.
- 7. Stunting:** defined as length for age less than 2 SD (WHO GROWTH CHART)
 - 8. Wasting:** defined as low weight for height, less than 2 SD (WHO Growth Chart).
 - 9. Adequacy of Complementary Feeding** was assessed using Infant and Child Feeding Index Score (WHO and UNICEF) and its association with nutritional status of the child was calculated.

Scoring For Child Complementary Feeding Index		
Breast Feeding Done	YES=2, NO=0	
Bottles Used	YES=0, NO=1	
Initiation of semisolid food, soft food at 6-8 months	YES=2 ,NO=0	
Dietary Diversity (24 Hrs) :		
Use of food group		
breast milk;(INCLUDED IN 2017) grains, roots and tubers; legumes and nuts; dairy products (milk, yogurt, cheese); flesh foods (meat, fish, poultry, liver or other organs); eggs; vitamin A-rich fruits and vegetables; and other fruits and vegetables		0=0 1-4=1 5 or More=2

Food Frequency (past 7 days)			
For egg/ poultry/meat/fish	0 times in past 7 days=0 1-3 times in past 7 days= 1 4 or more times in past 7 days= 2		
For staples	0-2 times=0 3 plus times=1		
Food Frequency= Sum of The Scores			
Meal Frequency (Past 24 Hrs)			
6-9 months	9-12 months	12-24 months	Total Score=12
0 meals/d = 0	0 meals/d = 0	0-1 meals/d = 0	
1 meals/d = 1	1-2 meals/d = 1	2-3 meals/d = 1	
2 meals/d = 2	3+ meals/d = 2	4+ meals/d = 2	
Scoring of Adequate Practices			
0-4=Low	5-8=Average	9-12=High	

Data Analysis: Data were presented in the form of percentage, mean; SD. Chi square test was applied to examine association between socio demographic and complementary feeding variables. Univariate analysis and multivariate logistic regression was

done to ascertain association between socio demographic variables and nutritional status indicators. Data was analysed using Epi-info/ SPSS software.

Observation:

Table 1: Maternal Characteristics and Socio demographic Profile

Maternal Age (in yrs)	n	%
<25	127	34.32%
25-30	189	51.08%
>30	54	14.59%
Maternal Education		
No formal education	106	28.6%
Primary education	134	36.2%
Secondary Education	92	24.8%
Higher Education	38	10.2%
Caste and Tribe		
Tribal	63	17.02%
Nontribal	307	82.9%
Maternal Employment Status		
Working	108	29.18%
Non Working	262	70.8%
Type of Delivery		
NVD	212	57.29%
C-Section	158	42.70%
Place of Delivery		
Govt. Setup	198	53.51%
Private Setup	172	46.48%
Family Income (per month)		
<5000	71	19.18%
5000-10000	215	58.10%
>10000	84	22.70%

Table 2: Child characteristics and Anthropometry

Child's Age (In Months)	Number (N)	Percentage (%)
6-8 Months	67	18.10%
9-11 months	112	30.27%
12-24 Months	191	51.62%
Gender		
Male	236	63.78%
Female	134	36.21%
Length/Age		
<2 SD (Stunting)	141	38.10%
>2 SD(No Stunting)	229	61.89%
Weight/Length		
<2SD (Wasting)	97	26.21%
>SD (No Wasting)	273	73.78%

Table 3: Complementary Feeding Practices

Indicator	Number	Percentage
Continued Breastfeeding	134	36.2%
Bottle Feeding	107	28.9%
Initiation of Complementary Feeding at 6-8 Months	174	47.02%
Min. Meal Frequency	216	58.3`%
Minimum Dietary Diversity	53	14.3%
Minimum Acceptable Diet	35	9.4%

Table 4: Association of Complementary Feeding Practices to the Nutritional Status

Comp. Feeding indicators		Wasting(n=97)	P value	Stunting N= 141	P value
Continued breastfeeding n=134)	Present	26	0.03	44	0.14
	Absent	71		97	
Bottle feeding(n=107)	Present	36	0.05	46	0.2
	Absent	61		95	
Timely initiation of complementary feeding(n=174)	Present	44	0.05	55	0.01
	Absent	53		86	
Minimal meal frequency(n=216)	Met	41	0.9	59	0.9
	Not met	56		82	
Minimal dietary diversity(n=53)	Met	09	0.04	28	0.02
	Not met	88		113	
Minimal acceptable diet(n=35)	Met	04	0.05	09	0.05
	Not met	93		132	

Discussion

During infancy and early childhood (birth to 2 years), adequate amount of appropriate nutrition has paramount importance for full development of children's human potential. [8] This period is also regarded as "critical window" for child's health, growth, and development. Furthermore, reversing of stunting developed during this period is very difficult after the second anniversary of the children. As has been observed in most other developing countries, the traditional complementary foods have been reported to be grossly inadequate when compared to estimated needs. Existing literature for the nutrient density, energy levels, and adequacy of the amount consumed in comparison to their nutritional requirement are not consistent. [9]

Minimum dietary diversity observed by Dasgupta et al. (46%) and Reinbott et al. (44%). However, the lower prevalence was reported by Khan et al. (32.6%), Mukhopadhyay et al. (24.4%), Mondal et al. (30.85%), Parashar et al. (29.6%), and Bentley et al. (13%). Singhal et al. noted a higher prevalence of MDD (79.6%) in their study. [10]

Prevalence of Minimum Meal Frequency reported by Khan et al. is (48.6%). [11] However, Mondal et al., Bentley et al., Singhal et al., and Aemro et al., Rao et al. found a lower prevalence of MMF at 41.49%, 43%, 43.4%, 44.7%, and 32%, respectively. On the other hand, Reinbott et al., Mukhopadhyay et al., and Parashar et al. reported higher prevalence of MMF at 70%, 67.0%, and 77.8%–78.5%, respectively. [12]

Minimum adequate diet observations were made by researchers such as Mukhopadhyay et al. (31.5%), Singhal et al. [13] (37.7%). However, Reinbott et al., Khan et al., and Bentley et al. found a lower prevalence of MAD among children 6–23 months than the current study at 28%, 19.7%, 5%, respectively. On the other hand, Khanna et al. reported higher prevalence of MAD (65.95%). [14]

Dasgupta et al. observed a significant association between MDD and sex of child. Parashar et al. in their study observed that minimum diversity was significantly associated with the area of residence. Aemro et al. in their study found that significant association exists between MDD and birth order, mother's education, and area of residence socioeconomic status. Khanal et al. reported a significant association of MDD with birth order, place of delivery, mode of delivery, mother's education, area of residence, religion, socioeconomic status, and antenatal care. [15]

Dasgupta et al. in their study found that the prevalence of MMF was significantly associated with the literacy status of mother. Parashar et al. found that the prevalence of MMF was significantly associated with area of residence. Aemro et al. revealed that the prevalence of MMF was significantly related with the birth order of child, mother's education, socioeconomic status, and antenatal care. In a study done by Khanal et al., it was observed that significant association exists between the prevalence of MMF and maternal education, antenatal care. [16]

The prevalence of MAD was significantly associated with area of residence, sex of child, birth order of child, and SLI. Dasgupta et al. found that the prevalence of MAD was significantly associated with sex of child. [17] The study done by Khanal et al. found that there was significant association between MAD and place and mode of delivery, mother's age, and education.

Scientific merits of the study: The age of 6- 23 months is the longest period in the “first 1000 days of life”. This period is called the window of opportunity and is the important stage to optimize child growth and development in order to prevent malnutrition, including wasting and stunting, as well as the negative consequences in the adulthood. The assessment of complementary feeding adequacy and its association with the nutritional status will reinforce the importance of timely initiation of complementary feeding.

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